

Liveness, Code, and DeadCode in Code Jockeying Practice

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Abstract

This paper explores notions of ‘liveness’ and ‘code’ to situate emerging Code Jockeying (CJing) practices in reference to Live Coding and blank-slate improvisation. Chun’s (2008) notion of ‘source code as fetish’ and theory on slow design are employed to critique compulsions in Live Coding towards code, liveness, and ephemerality. It is suggested that CJing evokes different manifestations of liveness and code, perhaps deviating from celebrated blank-slate approaches. The DeadCode (Dead) CJing software is presented; a browser-based, tablet-friendly, and language-agnostic CJing interface that supports improvised mixing of pre-written code (‘deadcode’), different code projections for audience members and performers, and gestural controls. Dead’s divergence from both liveness and normative representations of code are examined, inviting criticism as to whether the use of Dead still constitutes ‘Live Coding’.

Introduction

Both ‘liveness’ and ‘code’ are celebrated components of Live Coding which have provided useful for situating Live Coding within a broader New Media landscape. Liveness in performance has been closely associated with improvisation, as Magnusson (2014, p. 22) articulates in stating that the “default mode of live coding performance is improvisation”. Blank-slate live coding, in which the performer begins from a blank interface and develops their performance from scratch (Collins and McLean 2014), is one mode of performance that especially exhibits livness and improvisation. Such practices have been framed in distinction from other forms of computer-mediated audio-visual performance that have been critiqued in Live Coding literature for being overly contrived. For instance, Parkinson and Bell (2015) distinguish the ‘we all hit play’ performance practices of electronic dance music producer deadmau5, from those of free improvisation jazz guitarist Derek Bailey and argue that Live Coding more resembles the latter.

Earlier literature has also differentiated Live Coding from other

forms of computer art that rely on conventional Digital Audio Workstations (DAWs) and other graphical user interfaces (GUIs). Collins et. al (2003) suggest that part of the reason Live Coders gravitate towards code rather than DAWs such as Ableton Live or Reason is to escape the rigidity of such “fixed interfaces” in favor of more improvisational, live, and perhaps risky tools. Blackwell and Collins (2005) similarly contrast Ableton Live with the ChucK (Wang et. al 2015) Live Coding language. More recent research has explored the continuum between highly graphical interfaces and text-based programming languages, augmenting GUIs with scripting capabilities, and vice-versa (e.g. Gibber (Roberts and Kuchera-Morin 2012), Gibberwocky (Roberts and Wakefield 2016), and Visor (Purvis et. Al 2019))

The Live Coding practice of sharing one’s screen aims to achieve transparency and performance theatrics through both liveness and code. Code provides a declarative expression of the performer’s creative process, while its projection serves to convince an audience of its live composition. The TOPLAP Manifesto Draft (TOPLAP 2010) suggests that this composition of liveness and code distinguishes Live Coding from more obscurant performance practices, in which the audience cannot be confident that the performer has not just hit play on a pre-recorded set and is checking their emails. Moreover, as Rohrer et. al (2007) articulate, the practice of sharing one’s screen in live performance can facilitate “public reasoning” between performers and audience members over processes that are normally deliberated behind the closed doors of a studio. While compulsions towards both ‘liveness’ and ‘code’ have motivated exciting new forms of expression that challenge and build upon previous forms of computer-mediated art, both performance qualities can be critiqued in light of the established and continually evolving practices of Live Coding. This paper explores some of these critiques and situates Code Jockeying (CJing) as a hybrid practice that combines elements of Live Coding with other audio-visual performance practices that were once framed in opposition to (or to some extent separate from) Live Coding. Such opposing practices include dependency on pre-scripted content, heavy

reliance on graphical software abstractions, and other deviations from ‘liveness’ and ‘code’.

The proceeding section employs Chun’s (2008) conception of code as fetish to challenge practices that position source code at the center of Live Coding. The temporal politics of liveness, speed, and ephemerality in Live Coding are then likened to the precarity of the entrepreneurial ‘gig economy’. The DeadCode (Dead) CJing software is introduced and examined, indicating how it responds to some of the critiques presented while also perhaps diverging from the principles that initially distinguished Live Coding from other forms of computer-mediated art.

Live Coding and Code Fetishism

In ‘On “Sourcery,” or Code as Fetish’, Chun (2008, p. 301) critiques how “software has recently been posited as the essence of new media, and knowing software as a form of enlightenment”. For instance, speaking in reference to the free and open-source software movement, Chun (2008, p. 303) highlights how “insisting that freedom stems from free software ... amplifies the power of source code, erasing the vicissitudes of execution and the structures that ensure the coincidence of code and its execution”. Moreover, Chun (2008, p. 311) cautions how “we “primitive folk” worship source code as a magical entity-as a source of causality- when in truth the power lies elsewhere, most importantly in social and machinic relations”.

Live Coding practices that (at least superficially) organize around code can be critically examined under Chun’s insights. Chun might caution against allowing the software employed in Live Coding performance to stand-in for the motivations that have evolved around Live Coding. This sentiment is also reflected in the TOPLAP Manifesto Draft (TOPLAP 2010) which states that “Live Coding is not about tools”.

The practice of sharing one’s screen in Live Coding performance can be dissected to illustrate Chun’s cautions. In Live Coding performances, the projected code is often a central focal point. A literal

interpretation of ‘show us your screens’ could allow a performer to claim transparency and liveness on the basis that they presented a flood of text too small for an audience to interpret. Code fetishism risks equating adherence to the medium of code (and its projection) as Live Coding; as transparent, live, theatrical, cutting-edge, and experimental.

Conversely, code can also be employed obfuscate and mask hidden operations and intentions. High-level abstractions and ‘impure’ functions that have many side-effects may present to an audience as a single operation (what would Live Coding’s equivalent of lip-syncing look like?). To this point, Chun (2008, p. 315) adds that “we know very well that source code is not executable”; source code’s transition to action contains steps of translation, both social and technical, that are erased when source code is perceived as immediately executable.

In the TOPLAP manifesto, “show us your screens” is preceded by “obscurantism is dangerous” (TOPLAP 2010), suggesting that at least part of the reason code is projected is to provide transparency. Technocratic obscurantism behind source code that is deceitfully presented in the name of transparency has the potential to be more obscurant than admitting to “just hitting play” (Parkinson and Bell 2015) on a pre-mixed performance. In sum then, interfaces that glorify or aestheticize the complexity of code may reify the performer’s ‘sourcery’ and the relations of knowledge-power that Live Coding seems vested in disrupting.

Liveness, Ephemerality and Speed

The venerated qualities of liveness, improvisation, and speed in some Live Coding performance settings can also be re-examined in light of critiques of the accelerated temporal qualities of technology. Rosa (2013) identified a paradox in which accelerations in technological progress have been accompanied by parallel accelerations in the perceived ‘pace of life’. Information communications technologies that promised to provide conveniences that would free up one’s time instead impose new temporal demands, manifested in ubiquitous con-

nectivity. Time that is relinquished by modern technologies is often expected to be redirected towards “displaying competent – which is to say profitable – subjectivity” (Gregg 2018, p. 188). Rosa (2013) argues that tendencies towards speed are driven by cultural, economic, and structural motors.

In response to social acceleration, critical theorists and technologists have compelled further appreciation for, and exploration of ‘slowness’ and its qualities. Walter Benjamin (1983) offered the icon of the flâneur; an urban roamer who juxtaposes their inherent appreciation of their activity against their busy industrial backdrop. Compulsions for slow interaction have also manifested in the philosophy and design of slow technologies. Strauss and Faud-Luke (2009) advocate for a form of ‘slow design’ that facilitates reflection, sustainability, and other qualities beyond utility. Hallnäs (2015) similarly articulates slow technologies as artefacts of expression that reveal their profundity through use, rather than the functional role they fulfill. Odom et. al (2012), Odom (2015), and Grosse-Hering et. al (2013) have employed principles of slow design in the creation of new technologies that counterbalance the perceived accelerations brought by ubiquitous media. Taken together, these works identify a potentially harmful social (or market) preference trending towards efficiency and speed, and propose designed slowness as one response.

In alignment with these slow philosophies, “Slow Coding” (Hall 2007) has been suggested as a practice of Live Coding that celebrates a “non-competitive, meditative, conversational ethos” rather than virtuosity and danger. However, compulsions towards ‘liveness’ in Live Coding often favour speed and ephemerality (for instance, in the context of an Algrave performance). Improvisation without the aid of graphical abstractions requires the performer to be mentally and physically dexterous so not to subject an audience to stagnant aesthetic results. Code is generated and subsequently vanishes as quickly as the duration of a half-hour Algrave set, providing little opportunity to experiment with longer compositional forms. Indeed, Slow Coding seems to juxtapose other articulations of Live Coding that emphasize efficiency and speed in such performance situations. For instance,

McLean and Wiggins (2010a, p.8) suggest one goal of bricolage and interactive programming to “provide a more efficient creative feedback loop”. Similarly, the TidalCycles live coding language has aligned its development towards “terse syntax [that] allows for faster expression of ideas, and therefore a tighter programmer feedback loop more suitable for creative tasks” (McLean and Wiggins 2010b, p.2, emphasis added).

Chun’s problematization of the conception of immediate program execution suggests that the prospect of ‘live’ program execution may erase other steps that are necessary for translating code into executable binary (or perceived action more broadly) and thereby serve to reify source code as the essence of new media. A Live Coding performance may be reduced to the performer’s code as it is created ‘live’, negligent of hours of rehearsal, prior software development, pre-programming, community building, and other factors that produce such spectacles.

‘Fast’ blank-slate Live Coding practices that celebrate the ephemerality of code may also subject the performer to a form of precarity familiar to the contemporary ‘gig economy’. In blank-slate performances, the performer often discards all written code at the end. Like the gigger’s employment, code is impermanent, undependable, and prone to termination. Parkinson and Bell (2015) illustrate a connection between the ‘liveness’ of a performance and the audience’s perception of the performer’s labor. They note that performances are seen as more ‘live’ when it appears that the performer exerts significant labor. Thus to classify as ‘live’ and improvisational, Live Coder’s may be asked to exert greater labor while also accepting that the results of their efforts (or at least their code) will soon vanish. Parallels can be observed with how ‘gigs’ demand significant labor while failing to provide persistent economic security. In both situations, compulsions towards speed (in code or employment turnover) enable precarious labor conditions. An appreciation for ‘slow’ qualities, graphical abstractions, and pre-written code has informed the design of the Dead CJing software presented here, reflecting an attempt to balance liveness and ephemerality with persistence and

security.

Code and Liveness in Code Jockeying

Code Jockeying (CJing) (Collins and McLean 2014; Purvis et. al 2019) is an approach to Live Coding in which the performer is primarily concerned with transitioning between pre-written code snippets, rather than generating new ones live. Liveness and improvisation in CJing practice focus on discovering new combinations of code snippets and orchestrating their timely execution. CJing can be seen as a different flavor of Live Coding than the blank-slate approach discussed, with its own different expressions of ‘code’ and ‘liveness’.

Purvis et. al (2019) identified usability limitations of text-based code interfaces for CJing, proposing a suite of gesture-based abstractions (sliders, knobs, MIDI controller inputs) to supplement text-based code in their Visor Live Coding environment. Salazar’s (2017) tablet-based Auraglyph software has similarly been motivated by a desire to find gesture in Live Coding, beyond text-based interfaces.

Such motivations to replace or augment text-based interface with continuous controls and gesture-based interactions suggest a desire to transcend a particular manifestation of code fetishism that only recognizes text-based code. When source code is understood not to be ‘executable’ (as Chun advocates), abstractions such as sliders and MIDI controllers no longer appear to be impurities of otherwise pure and transparent source code; source code is impure from the start and gestural widgets (impurely) continue without claiming higher-order transparency. The emerging practices and software surrounding CJing thus continue to question what counts as ‘code’, at what point CJing software becomes the same DJ/VJ software that earlier Live Coding literature began to deviate from in the first place, and whether or not it is even desirable to erect such distinctions between code and not-code. The Dead CJing software continues this discussion.

Purvis et. al (2019, p.2) also note the “the difficulty of reusing and sharing content in audiovisual tools” (emphasis added) as a motivation informing the development of the Visor CJing environ-

ment. By deliberately encouraging the preparation and reuse of code, CJing seems to deviate from the form of improvisation, liveness, and ephemerality discussed earlier. Code written for CJing must have persistence beyond a single performance (unlike blank-slate live coding) to enable the performer to explore new forms of improvisation. However, reliance on previously-written code could enable performance practices similar to the ‘we all hit play’ philosophy of deadmau5, in which the performer merely hits play on a pre-recorded set. Parkinson and Bell (2015, p.1) articulate how deadmau5’s “notion of performance as spectacle” deviates from Live Coding’s orientation towards free improvisation.

Provided these perspectives, CJing appears to either challenge or extend earlier mandates of Live Coding in their conceptions of both liveness and code. The following section introduces the Dead CJing software and its motivations to either redefine or deviate from liveness and code.

DeadCode

Dead is a browser-based, language-agnostic, and tablet-friendly environment for audio-visual live coding and Code Jockeying (see Figure 1). Dead provides an interface for authoring code snippets that can be toggled on and off on a grid of buttons (called ‘stems’). The interface contains sliders and other control inputs to facilitate smooth transitioning between stems and ‘tracks’ (columns of stems). Currently Dead supports the TidalCycles (McLean and Wiggins 2010b) and Hydra (Jack, n.d.) live coding languages, with the capability to include renderers for other languages in future versions.

Motivations

Dead was conceived as the improbable combination of the TidalCycles (McLean and Wiggins 2010b) live coding language, and the Ableton Live DAW. Dead draws inspiration from Ableton’s ‘scene launcher’ interface which enables the user to create a performance workflow

while composing in the DAW, while underlying sound and visuals are generated by TidalCycles and Hydra respectively. Earlier it was discussed how Live Coding has been articulated as a practice separate from conventional Ableton Live performances and similar forms of computer-mediated audio-visual expression. However, perhaps one of Ableton Live’s most attractive features is its balance of static composition and live performance. Artists using Live can pre-craft well-produced sound layers (a less ‘live’ practice) and then use Live’s scene launcher interface to perform with them live. To support CJing, Dead aims to strike a similar balance by supporting both static composition and improvised exploration and editing of pre-composed stems.

In response to the earlier discussion on liveness and the ephemeral precariousness of blank-slate live coding, a core design goal of Dead was to facilitate the persistence and reuse of pre-written code. For the author, it was frustrating not to have an organized method for reusing or remixing code snippets produced from successful improvisation sessions. Dead seeks to address this issue by providing an interface that can support both persistence and improvisational exploration. For instance, a common workflow that has been established by using Dead includes starting with an improvisation using one of Stem code editors, producing a desired aesthetic result, and then separating the code into multiple stems (e.g. a different stem for bass, drums, and visuals). After several iterations, the Dead Launch Space will contain a library of Stems that facilitate improvised exploration of new permutations and modifications of layers. The interface places no restrictions on how many stems can be added, permitting Dead compositions to grow arbitrarily large. To support this persistence, it was important early in development to implement basic operations for saving and loading state, as well as moving and managing stems (e.g. with copy and paste commands). The state of a Dead composition can be saved to the browser storage with the keyboard shortcut ‘CTRL+s’ and loaded from browser storage with ‘CTRL+l’, or saved to a JSON file with ‘CTRL+d’ and opened with ‘CTRL+o’.

A second goal of the interface was to provide gestural abstractions from the code to allow easier continuous control of parameters and in-

Figure 1: DeadCode interface

stantaneous toggling of code execution. In this regard, Dead has been motivated by several previous Live Coding environments that have supported gestural abstractions, including Visor (Purvis et. al 2019), Auraglyph (Salazar 2017), and Estuary (Ogborn et. al 2017). Continuous controls can be challenging to type in text-based live coding environments, usually requiring the performer to repeatedly delete, modify, and re-run small changes to parameters. Such discretized motions can often only be performed one-at-a-time by a single performer. To transition between records, Disc Jockeys typically need to modulate several parameters at once (for instance filtering out bass frequencies from the out-going track while increasing the bass of an incoming track). To enable the performer to execute multiple actions at once, Dead has been designed for tablets. The performer can simultaneously apply a filter, turn off a code stem, and introduce a new stem with a multi-touch gesture.

Dead’s primary design goals towards persistence and graphical interfaces could be seen as deviations from both ‘liveness’ and ‘code’. A discussion of whether Dead violates any necessary conditions of Live Coding follows after a complete overview of the software.

Design and Features

The majority of the Dead interface is composed of the ‘Launch Space’; columns of ‘stems’ represented by buttons that can be started and stopped by clicking or tapping a stem button. When a stem button is clicked, the code underlying that stem is executed, and when a stem is turned off, its code is stopped. Vertical sliders are fixed to the bottom of each stem column for controlling the volume of all stems in that column.

Right-clicking (or long-pressing on tablets) on a stem button opens it in the ‘Stem Editor’ panel on the right of the interface (see Figure 2). In the Stem Editor, the user can write code that will be executed when that stem is turned on. If the stem is already toggled on, code that is evaluated in the Stem editor (by clicking ‘Eval’, or toggling the code editor to be ‘Live’) evaluates the code immediately, enabling

the user to improvise during a CJing performance. The Stem Editor also contains horizontal sliders for other effects suited to a continuous range, and code toggles for quickly applying and removing effects to the stem. A ‘Master’ menu also persists in the Stem Editor, for setting the tempo, applying global effects, and defining code macros that are executed before rendering stems.

Figure 2: DeadCode Stem Editor panel (bordered in red)

The final component in the bottom right corner of the Dead interface includes the ‘Render View’ (see Figure 3). The Render View contains a projection of the active code (ie. the combination of all stems that are turned on) and any rendering visuals. A copy of the

Render View can be popped out into another full-screen window to display to an audience.

Rendering and Language Neutrality

Dead has been designed to be language-agnostic, employing a similar architecture to the Extramuros (Ogborn et. al 2015) collaborative live coding environment. While the current version supports only TidalCycles and Hydra, the render engine can be easily updated to support more languages. For rendering TidalCycles, each stem is appended to a ‘stack’ expression, with any applied effects prepended. For instance, the following pseudo-code may be generated by a Dead composition that has two active stems, and a global ‘gain’ effect applied:

```
d1 $ (|* gain 0.9) $ stack [  
  (* lpf ‘‘900’’) $ s ‘‘bd cp’’, --stem 1 with a low  
    pass filter effect  
  s ‘‘~ hh ~ hh’’           -- stem 2  
]
```

The TidalCycles code generated by Dead is passed via WebSockets to a client NodeJS application which pipes it to a Haskell interpreter, employing a method introduced by Extramuros (Ogborn et. al 2015). This approach is extensible to Live Coding languages that cannot be directly evaluated in the browser.

Hydra stems are similarly combined into a single Hydra expression, by ‘adding’ the output of different stems. For instance, two stems containing different Hydra oscillator generators (bolded) would be combined as follows:

```
osc(1,0.5,0.95).add(osc(4,0.5,0.3).rotate(0.6)).out()
```

Future iterations of the software will add different options for how Hydra stems are combined (eg. Hydra’s ‘blend’, ‘diff’, ‘modulate’, or

‘mult’ operators could be used in place of ‘add’).

Modes of Liveness

Tanimoto (1990) has described the various levels of liveness of programming languages, ranging from relatively static languages that require compilation before execution, to languages that execute as soon as code is written. Live coding languages are often interpreted to support more immediate execution than is possible with compiled languages. Ogborn et. al (2017) provide an overview of some different approaches to liveness employed by Live Coding environments. They note that structure editors such as those offered by Estuary and patcher languages (such as Max/MSP and PureData) can offer immediate execution since they prohibit syntactically invalid expressions that may otherwise occur (eg. in text-based editors) while transitioning from one state of the code to the desired expression. The LiveCodeLab Live Coding environment (Della Cassa and John 2014) proposes an alternative method to achieve immediate execution in a text-based editor, in which code is interpreted immediately, but syntactically invalid expressions are not executed.

Dead offers four distinct levels of liveness. All changes made to sliders in Dead are immediately executed (they are L4 live in Tanimoto’s (1990) terminology). Code editors in Dead offer two levels of liveness (see Figure 4). When the ‘live’ toggle is switched off, the user must either click ‘Eval’ or hit ‘SHIFT+enter’ on their keyboard for code to be evaluated. When the ‘live’ toggle is on, code is evaluated after a configurable amount of time (one second by default) has elapsed since the last keypress. This ‘debounced liveness’ (termed after the common JavaScript ‘debounce’ utility for delaying events) provides an alternative method for achieving near-live execution of text-based live coding languages while avoiding show-stopping crashes that could occur if the code was executed on each keypress. The performer is permitted to ‘finish their thought’ before execution occurs, and can choose to delay execution by ‘stammering’ (continuously typing and deleting a character).

Figure 4: DeadCode code editor with language selection and liveness toggle

From one perspective, Dead’s support for the persistence and reuse of code can be interpreted as a fourth level of liveness. Code that is pre-written rather than being authored live (termed here as ‘dead-code’) has endured a longer process of translation from source code to executable before it is ultimately rendered in front of an audience. The performer’s preparatory labor in composing the code, arranging it into navigable labeled ‘stems’, and other production tweaks can be considered a process of compilation, while execution occurs when that code is invoked in performance. This interpretation of the liveness of deadcode acknowledges the labor involved in such tasks of compila-

tion as a requisite component of CJing performances while maintaining a distinction between such practices and more live blank-slate approaches. Furthermore, framing deadcoding (the act of creating pre-written code for later performance) as compilation, and performance as execution appropriately recognizes the ‘live’ aspect of CJing as the timely rendering of code in arrangement with other interacting elements.

Multiple Projections for ‘Showing Us Your Screen’

In Live Coding performances, the aesthetic of the code is often enough to provide the audience with both ‘access to the performer’s mind’ and something interesting to view, while the interface provides a more functional role. In earlier versions of Dead, it was unclear how the performer would ‘show their screen’ when their screen was primarily occupied by a functional interface that conceals most of the underlying code. To address this issue, the ‘Render View’ was added to the bottom right corner of the Dead interface. The Render View contains the code of all active stems overlain on top of the currently rendered Hydra visuals. For performances, new instances of the Render View can be cloned to new windows to present multiple full-screen views to the audience, while the performer can still view the visual output of their performance in the bottom right corner of the performance interface. This approach was motivated by Estuary’s (Ogborn et. al 2017) similar capabilities to provide multiple different projections of the same code to suit different viewers and users. The audience is provided a projection that aligns with the aesthetics of a live coding performance, while the performer can control audio-visual results with a more functional projection. Dead’s Render View was also informed by VJing software which conventionally allocates a portion of the interface for viewing the video material displayed to the audience.

Architecture and Implementation

Dead was written in JavaScript using the ReactJS/Redux frontend libraries. Live Coding languages used in Dead that cannot be rendered directly in the browser (currently only TidalCycles) are sent over a WebSocket connection to a NodeJS server run locally on the performer's machine and then are piped to the appropriate interpreter. The Dead performance interface communicates with all instances of the Render View via browser post messages. Dead uses the browser's local storage to save state, or users can download a JSON file of their Dead composition and load it back into the browser. Figure 5 provides an overview of the Dead architecture.

Is it Live? Is it Code?

The primary design goals of Dead were to deviate from both liveness and code in preference of a more gesture-based and persistent interface suited to CJing. Therefore, it seems reasonable to question whether the resulting design still qualifies as Live Coding.

The pre-programming encouraged by Dead seems to contrast with Live Coding's celebration of improvisation and uncertainty. In this way, Dead may deviate from McLean and Wiggins' (2010a) formulation of Live Coding as a 'bricolage' feedback loop between the performer and their machine. Deadcode is generally predictable to the performer. However, the CJing practice supported by Dead facilitates another feedback loop between the performer and the audience that requires another form of improvisation. Similar to DJs and VJs, CJs are tasked with reading their audience to appropriately curate new material to play. Furthermore, unlike most DJ software, the Dead performance interface affords the live alteration of the underlying sound-generation algorithms, and live composition of new stems. Thus while Dead perhaps sacrifices liveness by encouraging pre-programming, it also offers new expressions of liveness consistent with DJ improvisation.

The TOPLAP manifesto's call to 'show us your screens' is also

challenged or stretched by Dead. Dead's Render View offers a projection of the code behind currently executed stems to achieve an aesthetic and practice aligned with the common Live Coding tradition of projecting code for the audience. However, as has been discussed, part of the reason Live Coding artists project their code is to provide transparency with regards to what the performer is doing on their computer (ie. not 'just hitting play' and checking emails). A nefarious Render View could easily provide the illusion of liveness, improvisation, and significant labor, while the performer merely hits play on a pre-recorded set. In many respects, such a misleading projection is not so different from the form of 'we all hit play' liveness practiced by deadmau5. As Parkinson and Bell (2015) note, in such performance situations, liveness resides in the spectacle of the performance (the 'Render View'), rather than improvisation. While Dead does not support such views by default, it is noted that projections could enable the form of obscurantism that Live Coding has sought to avoid.

Dead can be used to perform entirely with buttons and sliders, requiring no manipulation of the code underlying each stem. It can be questioned then, whether Dead qualifies as 'coding' to contribute to a continuing discussion in the Live Coding community as to what qualifies as code, and whether or not drawing such distinctions is desired. Beyond just text-based programming languages, the Live Coding community has recognized visual (Max/MSP, PureData), tactile (Cocker 2015), embodied (Baalman 2015), and esoteric representations of code (to name only a few). Defining an exclusive set of expressions of algorithms to qualify as code, therefore, seems capricious, and any definition of 'Live Coding' based on such criteria would be fragile. The earlier discussion of misleading projections of code (for instance in a nefarious Render View) demonstrates how any algorithmic process can trivially be translated into text instructions that satisfy a normative representation of 'code'. Therefore, this paper affirms in concert with Chun (2008), that the essence of Live Coding should not be located in a transfixed representation of code. Stated differently, this paper argues that the 'code' in Live Coding should be

Figure 5: System overview

permitted to breathe into new representations. Whether or not the specific representation presented by Dead qualifies under this broader interpretation is open to scrutiny.

Future Work and TODOs

While this paper has focused primarily on the ‘liveness’ and ‘code’ aspects in investigating how CJing and the Dead environment fit within Live Coding, clearly there are other aspects of Live Coding that could have been examined. This paper could have also explored how open source software, networked performance, language neutrality, collaboration, community organization, experimentation, Algorave, and other characteristics of Live Coding are (or are not) repre-

sented in Dead’s design and use. Such factors could be the subject of future research and suggest several agenda items for the continuing development of the Dead software.

Future development efforts will focus on providing renderers for more Live Coding languages, including but not limited to SuperCollider (McCartney 2002), Gibber (Roberts and Kuchera-Morin 2012), The Force (Lawson n.d.), and Punctual (Ogborn n.d.). Another priority development item will be to support networked collaboration using Dead. One approach could employ a NodeJS WebSocket server application to share state to connected clients (similar to the Extramuros’ (Ogborn et. al 2015) server architecture). A secondary objective in supporting networked collaboration may include the creation of a more substantial back end system for sharing Dead stems

and compositions (for instance as is supported by Gibber (Roberts and Kuchera-Morin 2012)). Since Dead will sometimes execute native code on the user's machine (eg. as is done with TidalCycles code that is piped to a GHC interpreter) a stem publishing system would require significant security oversight. Lastly, future work will employ the emerging Web MIDI API to offer support for MIDI inputs for controlling Dead. Since Dead's layout resembles Ableton Live, MIDI mappings will be created for Ableton hardware controllers.

Links

- Demonstration video: <https://youtu.be/nTBwdGbfmU>
- Source Code Repository: <https://github.com/JamieBeverley/DeadCode>

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